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Title:

Integrated Geometric Errors Simulation, Measurement and Compensation of Vertical Machining Centres

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Abstract: This Paper presents research on geometric errors of simulated geometry which are measured and compensate in vertical machining centres. There are many errors in CNC machine tools have effect on the accuracy and repeatability of manufacture. Most of these errors are based on specific parameters such as the strength and the stress, the dimensional deviations of the structure of the machine tool, thermal variations, cutting force induced errors and tool wear. In this paper machining system that simulates the dimensional and geometric errors of three real axes describes milling machining. In order to validate the system closed loop feedback system is provided which rectify as well as compensate the errors in order to present the reliability and accuracy of the software. An experiment has been conducted on a 3 axis vertical CNC milling machine; the results show that this method is efficiently effective and applicable on any multi axis machining operation.

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Abstract

This Paper presents research on geometric errors of simulated geometry which are measured and compensate in vertical machining centres. There are many errors in CNC machine tools have effect on the accuracy and repeatability of manufacture. Most of these errors are based on specific parameters such as the strength and the stress, the dimensional deviations of the structure of the machine tool, thermal variations, cutting force induced errors and tool wear. In this paper machining system that simulates the dimensional and geometric errors of three real axes describes milling machining. In order to validate the system closed loop feedback system is provided which rectify as well as compensate the errors in order to present the reliability and accuracy of the software. An experiment has been conducted on a 3 axis vertical CNC milling machine; the results show that this method is efficiently effective and applicable on any multi axis machining operation.

Keywords: Geometric errors, CMM Measurement, 3 axis CNC milling machine.

1. Introduction

One of the most crucial activities for a successful project management (production, planning and control) is the estimation of project time, cost and performance evaluation of the project. This is an early estimation process which is usually handled by highly skilled, in-house experts. One of the main obstacles in this process is to accurately define the relationship between product characteristics and the

construction/fabrication time necessary to manufacture the product and the errors which are occurred during simulation of a part. We will try to develop the model which will show that it is possible to achieve admissible accuracy of the estimation of project activity time more specifically simulated a part time by using easily obtainable input data and minimization of errors. Improves accuracy, reduce machining time, and improves precision parts. A.A.Kadir and Mohsen Soori, Behrooz Arezoo and Mohsen Habibi (2013 and 2011)^{1, 2} presented a comprehensive review of existing virtual systems such as Web-based systems virtual machine tools and mathematical models. In this paper a virtual machining system which simulates the dimensional and geometrical errors of real three-axis milling machining operations is described. The system can read the machining codes of parts and enforce 21 errors associated with linear and rotational motion axes in order to generate new codes to represent the actual machining operation. Shaowei Zhu, Guofu Ding Shengfeng Qin, JiangLei, LiZhuang, Kaiyin Yan et al.² (2012) proposed an integrated geometric error modelling, identification and compensation method. Especially, a novel geometric error identification method was developed for any rotation axis of multi-axis machine tools based on a ball-bar. In the machining process, many factors affect the machining accuracy such as kinematics errors, thermal errors, cutting force induced errors, servo errors and tool wear. Among them, the geometric error of machine tool components and structures is one of the biggest sources of inaccuracy.

2. Geometric Errors

2.1 Need for measurement of errors during Simulation

Geometric errors are mainly concerned with the errors in the structural elements of the machine tools. These errors affect the machine repeatability and kinematic accuracy which are inherent in machine tool. For a three axis milling machine there are 21 errors namely:

3 linear positioning errors, 6 straightness errors, 9 angular errors and 3 squareness errors.

Angular errors such as pitch roll and yaw errors are common causes of positioning errors.

Straightness errors seriously degrade machine tool performance and have a direct influence on the machine tool path accuracy.

Squareness between axes can seriously degrade machine tool performance by dimensional errors in produced parts.

These errors can be result of wear in machine tool guide ways. Also they can be due to accidents which may have damaged the machine tool structural in some way. Components of geometric error in three axis CNC milling as in table 1.1.

Nominal position of every point are shown by x,y,z. Positional errors of each point along x, y and z directions are $\delta x(x)$; $\delta y(y)$; $\delta z(z)$, where the first subscript refers to errors direction and second refers to moving direction. In the same way, $\delta y(x)$; $\delta z(x)$; $\delta x(y)$; $\delta z(y)$; $\delta x(z)$; $\delta y(z)$ are straightness errors. $\epsilon x(x)$; $\epsilon y(x)$; $\epsilon z(x)$; $\epsilon x(y)$; $\epsilon y(y)$;

$\varepsilon_z(y)$; $\varepsilon_x(z)$; $\varepsilon_y(z)$; $\varepsilon_z(z)$ are angular errors and $\psi_x(y)$; $\psi_x(z)$; $\psi_y(z)$ are squareness errors.

Table 1.1: Geometric error components for 3-axis CNC milling.

Error Component	Linear Displacement Error			Angular Errors		
				Roll,	Pitch,	Yaw
X- axis	$\delta x(x)$	$\delta y(x)$	$\delta z(x)$	$\varepsilon x(x)$	$\varepsilon y(x)$	$\varepsilon z(x)$
Y-axis	$\delta x(y)$	$\delta y(y)$	$\delta z(y)$	$\varepsilon x(y)$	$\varepsilon y(y)$	$\varepsilon z(y)$
Z-axis	$\delta x(z)$	$\delta y(z)$	$\delta z(z)$	$\varepsilon x(z)$	$\varepsilon y(z)$	$\varepsilon z(z)$
Squareness Errors	$\psi_x(y)$; $\psi_x(z)$; $\psi_y(z)$					

Lukasz CZERECH, Roman KACZYŃSKI, Andrzej WERNER et al.³ (2012) presented topic related with machining error correction for objects bounded by curvilinear surfaces manufactured on numerically controlled milling machine. Currently it is realized by two techniques. The first of them is called **ON-LINE** and requires continuous correction of tool path during the machining process. The second method called **OFF-LINE** is based on correction of machining control system outside the machine (on the basis of control measurement results). In this methodology of machining shape error correction with off-line technique (with no constant and direct connection to CNC machine tool).

Soichi Ibaraki and Wolfgang Knapp (2011)⁴ reviews indirect measurement schemes for machine tool kinematics, in which the tool centre position is measured as the super position of error motion of linear or rotary axes. Indirect measurement schemes for the kinematics of 3 orthogonal linear axes as well as the 5 axis kinematics with two rotary axes will be reviewed. This paper covers Numerical compensation, Geometric error parameters and Kinematic models of machine tool, Indirect measurement schemes for the kinematics of orthogonal 3 linear axes, Indirect measurement schemes for 5-axis kinematics with two rotary axes.

Chana Raksiri, Manukid Parnichkun (2004)⁵ proposes a new off line error compensation model by taking into accounting of geometric and cutting force induced errors in a 3-axis CNC milling machine. Geometric error estimation determined by back-propagation neural network is proposed and used separately in the geometric error compensation model. Likewise, cutting force induced error estimation by back-propagation neural network determined based on a flat end mill behaviour observation is proposed and used separately in the cutting force induced error compensation model.

2.2 Methods of measurement of geometric errors

Measuring the dimensional and geometric errors is carried out using laser interferometer, Co-ordinate Measuring Machine, 3D Probe Ball Bar system. In linear measurement, for forming the fixed length reference arm of the interferometer, one retro-reflector is secured to the beam-splitter. By moving the other retro-reflector relatively to the beam-splitter the variable length measurement arm will be formed. Any change in the separation between the measurement arm retro-reflector and beam-

splitter is tracked by the laser system. CMM measures all the possible coordinates in a modelled component in X, Y, Z direction.

2.3 Software for modelling and identifying geometric errors

In order to implement the proposed method, for modelling and identifying geometric errors software is developed in the present work. The ideal tool path (tool tip and tool orientation) and NC codes are generated by a CAD/CAM system such as MASTER CAM v 09. Having the machine tool errors, NC codes and the position of the work part on the table, input in the software, every geometric error parameter is calculated at each cutter path.

3. Validation

In order to experimentally validate the virtual machining software, two parts are considered. In first step, the machining of the free form surface of a part shown in figure 1 contains errors.

Fig. 1: Machining profile with job set up containing geometric errors.

In second step with same geometry considered in real machining environment with compensation of errors in figure 2. Two profiles compared using data obtained from a CMM machine. In the present work, geometrical errors of VF 30 CNC milling machine with FANUC Series *oi*-MD used for machining with job set up and dial indicator at zero on machine. The milling tool used for the process is a flat HSS end mill with 10 mm diameter, helix angle 30° and flute number 4. The material of the workpieces is OHNS EN 31. The profile has 6 mm fillet and 5 mm depth of cut. After supplying the measurement data and NC codes into the software, NC codes are generated and by applying stock changes errors enforced than the first profile.

Fig. 2: Machining profile with job set up compensation of geometric errors.

The machining tests were carried out and compared by CAD surface comparator software using the same setup of machine and cutting tool figure 3 shows profile of reduced geometric errors measured by CARLZEISS PRISMO-5 CMM machine.

Fig.3 Coordinate Measurement of selected profile points.

Table 3.1 shows the result data with errors and compensation of errors in mm.

Table 3.1 Geometric error compensation after machining

CO Ordinates in mm	DIFFERENCE IN ACTUAL & NOMINAL IN mm	ERROR COMPANSATE DATA IN mm
X 25	-0.0165	0.0000
X 50	-0.0133	-0.0075
Y 25	-0.0045	-0.0034
Y 60	-0.0089	-0.0070
Z 5	-0.0113	-0.0022
R 6	0.0031	-0.0089

4. Conclusion

In the present work, the errors of a 3 axis CNC milling machine tool are enforced with change in stock of profile while pocket mill. The input to the software is the NC part programme of a specific 3 axis machine tool. The output of the system is the new NC

programme with change in stock which will visualize tool path more realistically causes reduced in machining time up to 10%, precession and high accuracy of part up to 40 to 50%. The approach used in the present work can also be developed further and applied to 5-axis CNC milling machines carried out with 39 geometric and dimensional errors. This is the subject of the future research of the authors.

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